

Impact of Climate Change on Smallholder Women Rice Farmers in Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria, 2012 - 2022

Braimah, Abdulrasak Lucky^a, Andero, Hope Folake^b, Sule, Moses^c

^{a,b,&c}Department of History and International Studies,

Federal University Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria

*Correspondence author: braimahabdulrasak@gmail.com

PAPER KEYWORDS

ABSTRACT

Climate Change, Lokoja,
Smallholder Women
Rice farmers.

Climate change affects smallholder agriculture across Nigeria. Women rice farmers face higher exposure because of limited access to land, finance, and climate information. This paper examines climate change impacts on smallholder women rice farmers in Lokoja, Kogi State. It focuses on rainfall variability, flooding, temperature rise, poor adaptation mechanisms, and their effects on rice production, income, and livelihoods. The paper also discusses gender-specific constraints that shape women's adaptive capacity. This paper adopts a qualitative research method, relying on primary and secondary sources, and a purposive data sampling method was used in data gathering. Contextual and descriptive analyses were used to analyse primary data and secondary literature. The preliminary findings suggest that women constitute a significant portion of the agricultural workforce in Lokoja, but they face systemic barriers, including limited access to credit, land tenure issues, and a lack of climate-smart technologies that hinder their adaptive capacity. Also, the findings of the study show that climate risks reduce yields, increase production costs, and deepen economic vulnerability among smallholder women rice farmers in Lokoja. The paper argues that gender-responsive climate adaptation policies are needed to support women rice farmers in Lokoja and similar settings. The paper concludes with recommendations tailored towards smallholder women rice farmers. The paper recommends that institutional support systems must be strengthened to ensure that women are actively included in climate adaptation efforts. Climate adaptation training, early-warning systems, and agricultural extension services should be tailored to smallholder women rice farmers' needs and delivered through channels that are accessible to them.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19909249>

1.1. Introduction

The bank of the Niger River, stretching from Lokoja town to Koton Karfe in Kogi state, has become a bed of rice farming. The supply of water through the traditional FADAMA irrigation method and from the river Niger waters has made rice cultivation constant all year round. Significantly contributing to the economy of the area. Among the local rice farmers of this region, women form a considerable number, contributing not only in direct labour but also in rice processing and marketing.

However, in recent years, climate change has made flooding a recurring environmental issue along the floodplains of the river Niger. In the years 2012, 2020 and 2022, flooding affected a large part of Lokoja and communities along the Lokoja confluence rivers, causing significant economic and agricultural losses, as years' worth of farm work were swept away. Farmers who utilise the flood plains of the confluence rivers for rice cultivation were mostly affected by the series of floods. Not only were their cultivation destroyed, but grain stores and reserve near Lokoja's markets were submerged, ruined and washed away by the ravaging floods.

The destruction of rice farms along the Lokoja confluence rivers not only caused economic loss to the farmers but also contributed significantly to food insecurity within and around the state (Muhammad, 2012; FloodList, 2020). The overdependence on rice, not just locally but globally, by nearly half of the world's population as a major source of staple food, meant that a break in its supply could lead to food insecurity (Abdulazeez *et al.*, 2019; Shahbandeh, 2021). In Nigeria, rice is widely consumed across all ethnic groups and serves as a key source of daily nourishment (Olufemi *et al.*, 2023).

Rice farming involves complex cultivation and production processes that require constant monitoring and demand government intervention for sustainable growth in the sector. Just as women make up a significant share of the global agricultural labour force and account for nearly half of all agricultural workers, they remain a part of rice farming. According to the 2021 data from the International Rice Research Institute, it shows that at least 500 million women are engaged in rice cultivation worldwide (International Rice Research Institute, 2021). Women participate across the entire production chain, including land preparation, planting, weeding, harvesting, processing, and marketing. Evidence shows that women often spend more time in rice farming activities than men, who in many contexts participate mainly during peak production periods of about six months (Das *et al.*, 2022). However, much of women's agricultural labour remains unpaid and unrecognised, as it is often viewed as an extension of domestic responsibilities.

The cultivation of rice requires a good climate, adequate rainfall and fertile land. Rice production has been known to thrive well along river plains, the type which Lokoja and its environs provide. Along the river plain and banks of the confluence rivers, rice is extensively cultivated with visible evidence between Lokoja and Koto Karfe, forming a significant agricultural product. In recent years, Lokoja has been recognised as a key rice-producing zone in Kogi State alongside other major areas like Ibaji, Idah, Bassa, and Ejiba. The availability of water makes rice farming in Lokoja ideal for both rainy and dry season cultivation, with many smallholder farmers relying on rice farming for their economic survival.

Over the years, the state as well as the federal government has actively promoted rice production, establishing farms and irrigation projects in Lokoja through supported initiatives and projects like The Agro-Processing, Productivity Enhancement and Livelihood Improvement Support (APPEALS) and FADAMA projects. These projects are mostly targeted at men farmers, largely disfranchised women smallholder rice farmers. Such disfranchisement, which already negatively affects women, has worsened due to the impact of climate change.

This paper examines the impact of climate change-induced flooding on smallholder women rice farmers in Lokoja and its environs. It highlights how climate stress interacts with gender inequality to shape farming outcomes. Using a qualitative and descriptive approach, the study explores how climatic changes influence rice yields, household food security, and the socio-economic conditions of women farmers (Danjibo, 2019). Understanding these impacts is necessary for designing effective, gender-responsive climate adaptation strategies in Lokoja and similar flood-prone regions of Nigeria.

Literature Review

Olufemi et al. (2022) examine the effectiveness of Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) rice processing technologies among rice processors in Kogi State. The study shows that rice processing is dominated by women, with 91.1% of respondents being female and an average age of 47.6 years. Most respondents had low formal education, relying largely on extension agents as their main source of information. The findings indicate that JICA-supported technologies improved rice processing efficiency. However, the study focuses primarily on technology adoption and processing outcomes, with limited attention to how climate variability affects women's productivity, income stability, or labour burden.

Abdulazeez et al. (2019) assess the Kogi Accelerated Rice Production Programme (KARPP) and its contribution to rice production and economic diversification. The study finds rice farming to be profitable, with a reported return of ₦1.25 for every ₦1 invested. Despite increased incomes for some farmers, the authors observe significant income inequality among participants. While the study highlights livelihood diversification and policy support, it treats farmers as a homogeneous group and does not disaggregate impacts by gender or examine how climate shocks influence income volatility among women farmers.

Alabi et al. (2024) analyse factors influencing the adoption of recommended rice production practices in selected local government areas of Kogi State. The study emphasises the importance of improved agricultural technologies for increasing productivity among smallholder farmers. It recommends training, cooperative support, and access to farm machinery through public-private partnerships. Although the study acknowledges smallholder constraints, it does not account for climate stressors such as flooding, heat, or rainfall variability, nor does it examine how these factors affect women farmers differently.

Ahmed Tijani Yusuf et al. (2025) investigate challenges in implementing the Rice Anchor Borrowers Programme in Kogi State. The study highlights the role of smallholder rice farmers in food security and identifies weak policies, poor infrastructure, and limited stakeholder inclusion as barriers to productivity. The authors call for climate-resilient infrastructure and localised policy reforms. However, the analysis remains largely policy-focused and does not explore how climate-related risks directly affect women rice farmers' livelihoods and adaptive capacity.

From an environmental perspective, Ifatimehin et al. (2013) studied the impact of climate change on human comfort in Lokoja. Their findings show that rising temperatures and declining vegetation contribute to severe thermal discomfort, with associated health risks such as heat stress and headaches. While the study provides

important climatic context, it does not link these conditions to agricultural labour, farm productivity, or gendered exposure to climate stress.

Similarly, Okosun *et al.* (2025) assess the impact of flooding on Lokoja communities and identify climate change-induced floods as a major cause of farmland destruction and reduced agricultural output, particularly rice production. The study attributes flooding to heavy rainfall and dam water releases. Despite its relevance, the study does not disaggregate flood impacts by gender or examine how repeated flood events affect women's farming roles, assets, and recovery strategies.

Gap in the literature

Despite growing research on rice production, climate change, and agricultural policy in Kogi State, several gaps remain. Existing studies focus on technology adoption, productivity, and policy performance, with limited attention to climate change as a lived, long-term livelihood stressor. There is little empirical work centred specifically on smallholder women rice farmers, despite evidence that women dominate rice processing and contribute significantly to production. Most studies do not examine the gender-differentiated impacts of flooding, heat stress, and rainfall variability on farm labour, income stability, health, and adaptive strategies. The 2012 Lokoja flood, a critical climate event, is rarely analysed in relation to women rice farmers' experiences and long-term livelihood outcomes.

The period 2012–2022 lacks a focused, longitudinal analysis linking climate shocks to changes in women's rice farming practices, resilience, and vulnerability. Hence, this study addresses these gaps by examining the impact of climate change on smallholder women rice farmers in Lokoja between 2012 and 2022, with particular attention to flooding, temperature stress, and institutional responses. By foregrounding women's experiences, the study contributes to climate-agriculture literature that integrates gender, local ecology, and livelihood vulnerability, offering evidence relevant for climate adaptation, agricultural policy, and gender-responsive development planning.

1.2. Research Methods

This paper adopts a qualitative research method, relying on primary and secondary sources, and a purposive data sampling method was used in data gathering. Contextual and descriptive analyses were used to analyse primary and secondary data. Drawing from both primary and secondary data, including existing literature on climate change and flooding in Nigeria, with specific reference to Lokoja and Kogi State. This paper aims to reconstruct how climate change has affected women rice farmers in Lokoja, Kogi State. The paper examines the impacts of climate change on rice production and farmers' responses over time. Although climate change impacts are increasingly evident in Lokoja, the understanding of the phenomenon remains limited among many smallholder women rice farmers. This knowledge gap highlights the need for stronger government-led awareness and education programmes to improve smallholder women rice farmers' capacity to adapt. A descriptive analysis is employed to assess women rice farmers' understanding of climate change, government policy responses, and existing adaptation and resilience-building mechanisms. The central objective of this paper is to examine the impacts of climate change on rice farmers in Lokoja from 2012 to the present.

1.3. Results and Discussion

Rice Farming in Lokoja: A Historical Perspective

Rice farming in the Lokoja is strongly tied to hydro-ecological factors of the region, and the sustained growth of rice cultivation in the region is a testament to the region's long-standing role as an agricultural and commercial crossroads in Nigeria. Over the years, Lokoja has served as a critical hub that connects the north and south of the country. While Lokoja itself, as of today, is more of a residential town being the Kogi state capital, it still maintains a strong agro-culture and agricultural practice.

The geographical location of Lokoja, which lies at the confluence of the rivers Niger and Benue, ensures that the region is well watered all year round, with regular seasonal flooding, fertile ground for agricultural activities, especially the cultivation of rice, which thrives well on the river banks and the flood plains of the confluence rivers, making Lokoja a major hub for rice farming in Kogi state. Lokoja plays a critical role in the economic and cultural integration of Kogi state as well as Nigeria. The town has long been a meeting point for travellers who crisscross the country, becoming a hub for interaction between the south and north of the country.

Historically, the major economic activities of people of Lokoja are agriculture (farming, fishing, and pottery), trading and spinning, etc. The confluence at Lokoja and the fertile plains of the River Niger and Benue have long attracted people who settled along the banks of the rivers either for farming activities, fishing or commerce. In the pre-colonial times, agricultural activities thrived in Lokoja with a significant growth of settlers along the river bank, mostly people who had fled from slave raiders and found the area around the confluence of the rivers accommodating for agricultural activities. Many of the early settlers who formed the indigenous people of the area included the Oworo, Hausa, Ebira, Igala, and Bassa people (Ali, 2011; Ali and Nomishan, 2022).

The pre-colonial period was characterised by indigenous knowledge systems; hence, for their agricultural activities, the people of the area adopted the "Fadama" (floodplain) system, an indigenous agricultural irrigation concept which is still in use till today. Some farmers practised recession agriculture, planting rice and other produce as the annual floods subsided. However, by the colonial period, the commercial and economic activities in Lokoja grew exponentially, leading to the formalisation of the agricultural activities. The colonial government, having made Lokoja its administrative centre for the Northern region in 1900, sought to ensure food security for the growing urban population and the colonial civil service, and then introduced a more formal agricultural practice (Enesi, 2019). This period saw the introduction of new varieties of agricultural products and the beginning of a shift from purely subsistence farming to a more structured one.

In the post-independence Nigeria, there was an increase in local rice production in Lokoja and its environs that was further strengthened by the Nigeria government decision to ban the importation of rice in the 1970s and 80s, while promoting various nationwide agro-programmes such as the "Operation Feed the Nation" and the subsequent "Green Revolution", these programmes helped empowered local farmers with modern inputs (fertilizers and mechanization). However, studies show that many of the agricultural intervention programmes often favoured male-led cooperatives, beginning a trend of

gender-based marginalisation in agricultural resource distribution that persists (Onoja et al., 2024).

The creation of Kogi state on 27th August 1991 drove up urbanisation of Lokoja town, leading to population growth and a growing demand for food. In order to address these challenges, especially as it relates to food security, the subsequent state government invested in various farming projects through the FG and the World Bank. On December 16, 1991, the first of the major agricultural intervention programmes, the Kogi State Agricultural Development Programme (KADP), was established under Edict No. 12 of 1991, through the initial support of the World Bank and International Fund for Agricultural Development, which contributed 72.6% of its funding (Yusuf et al., 2025; Agbamu, 2015). KADP formed the primary state-level body for agricultural extension and rural development within the state, targeted at improving rural agriculture and agricultural extension services.

Between 1991 and 2022, the states, through their collaboration with the Federal government and other bodies, have engaged in various agricultural projects aimed at boosting agricultural production in the state. Interventions and projects such as the FADAMA I, FADAMA II, FADAMA III, Kogi Accelerated Rice Production Programme (KARPP), initiated in 2011, the APPEAL, and the Anchor Borrower Programme, initiated in 2016, were specifically targeted at improving rice farming (Abdulazeez et al., 2019; Agbamu, 2015). The adoption of these programmes accelerated the cultivation and production of rice in Lokoja, by 2022 Lokoja was officially recognised as a key rice-producing zone (Zone C) in Kogi State.

Other projects, such as the ACREsAL Project, were targeted at improving farmers' adaptation to climate change, building climate resilience and developing skills on mitigating environmental challenges. The ACREsAL's Community Revolving Funds (CRF), and provision of improved (high-yielding) seedlings to farmers in 19 northern States (Kogi State inclusive) with semi-arid landscapes; i.e., areas with low precipitation and sparse vegetation.

Evidence of Climate Change in Lokoja

Climate change is the drastic change in the weather and climatic patterns caused by human emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. This global phenomenon affects people in different regions to various degrees and forms. Across Nigeria, farmers are struggling to cope with the impact of Climate change, which includes erratic rainfall, drought, high temperature, flash flooding and desertification. In Nigeria, climate change presents a multi-dimensional crisis; it is no longer just an environmental concern, but a deep and central driver of instability which affect the nation in multiple ways.

Studies have shown that the impact of climate change in Nigeria manifests in diverse and devastating ways, ranging from socio-cultural destabilisation, forced migration, internal displacement, resource-based violence, chronic agricultural disruption, and local economic decline (Akinwale and Udochukwu, 2025). Across Nigeria, climate change impact has become evident, manifesting in various environmental incidents such as flooding in coastal states due to the rise in sea and ocean level, prolonged droughts in the northern part of the country, desertification and desert encroachment, deforestation, heighten temperature, among many other symptoms of climate change.

Though the impact is uneven across regions, some states are experiencing stronger physical and social impacts than others. However, climate change impacts are more pronounced in states and regions that depend more on primary means of production, such as agriculture. In the northern part of Nigeria, climate change-induced desertification and drought drive pastoralists southward, with many of the pastoralists settling in the north-central region, where their activities disrupt agricultural activities and, most times, lead to clashes (Ahmed et al.,2024; Itodo, 2017).

In 2012, the country witnessed a devastating flooding which affected 30 out of the 36 states of the nation. This catastrophe exposed the country's profound vulnerability and created an urgent impetus for a structured national response. That same year, the Federal government at the national level adopted the National Climate Change Policy 2012 (NCCP), a foundational document which seek to established a comprehensive framework to address the dual challenges of adaptation and mitigation and to integrate climate resilience into the county's national development plans, combat climate impacts like extreme weather and food insecurity, and pursue a low-carbon, high-growth economic pathway (FME, 2012).

In several parts of Nigeria, both seasonal and non-seasonal flooding have become more frequent due to erratic rainfall, with impacts growing in scale and intensity. At the same time, rising atmospheric temperatures have increased the occurrence of dry spells, particularly across the north-central region of the country. Because most agricultural activities in Nigeria are rain-fed, farming systems are highly sensitive to rainfall variability, temperature increases, and extreme weather events. As a result, agriculture remains highly vulnerable to climate change, with smallholder farmers who often lack the resources and technical capacity to manage climate shocks bearing the greatest burden.

In Kogi State, the impacts of climate change are increasingly visible, largely due to the state's geographical, ecological, and hydrological characteristics. The state lies within Nigeria's central floodplain system, which heightens exposure to both seasonal and flash flooding. In recent decades, changes in rainfall intensity and river discharge, combined with broader climatic shifts, have made flooding events more frequent and destructive. Data from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency indicate that the state is also experiencing increasingly erratic and unpredictable rainfall patterns alongside elevated atmospheric temperatures (Sunday and Aribisala, 2020).

Climate change impacts in other parts of Nigeria, particularly in the northern regions, have also contributed to the movement of pastoralists southward in search of grazing land. Lokoja has witnessed an influx of pastoralists, leading to frequent conflicts with farmers who report damage to farmlands by grazing herds. The nationwide flooding of 2012 caused extensive damage in Lokoja, washing away farmlands, disrupting agricultural activities, and resulting in losses valued at billions of naira. Similar levels of destruction were recorded during subsequent flood events in 2020 and 2022. Farming in Lokoja is mainly practised through rain-fed and Fadama irrigation systems. Consequently, a slight change in weather patterns can disrupt agricultural cycles, leading to crop losses or poor harvests. This high sensitivity to climate variability underscores the growing risks faced by farmers in the area.

Lokoja is located at the strategic confluence of the River Niger and the River Benue, serving as a major drainage basin for the two largest river systems in West Africa and one of the largest river confluences on the continent. While this confluence historically supported trade and provided fertile land for agriculture, it now represents a major climate risk due to recurrent flooding. Today, flooding in Lokoja constitutes one of the most significant environmental and climate challenges, directly disrupting agricultural activities. In this sense, the town's hydrological setting functions as a double-edged sword (Okosun *et al.*, 2025).

Rice farming is highly sensitive to climatic factors such as rainfall, water availability, and temperature (Abbas and Mayo, 2021). A slight change in rainfall volume or temperature can significantly affect rice productivity. Hence, rice farmers must carefully manage these elements throughout the growing period. In Lokoja and its environs, where rice is cultivated on floodplains and irrigation depends largely on river systems, both increases and decreases in river levels adversely affect farming activities. Traditionally, these farmers rely on predictable rainfall patterns, stable water levels, and the seasonal use of floodplains as planting beds. When these natural processes become unpredictable, they pose serious risks to rice production and farmers' livelihoods.

Participants explained that most rice farming practices they know rely on indigenous knowledge that has been passed down through generations. According to them, planting periods were traditionally determined by observing the natural cycle between planting and harvest, which was known to last about seven months. This local knowledge guided decisions on when to plant and harvest rice. Salamatu Mohammed explained that the timing of rice cultivation depended largely on weather conditions and the specific farming location. She noted that rice was usually planted along riverbanks only after floodwaters had receded. The residual moisture left in the soil after the river dried provided sufficient water to sustain rice growth until harvest.

She further described how farmers dug shallow channels within the riverbeds to allow water to spring up naturally. This water was then distributed to rice fields using irrigation machines. In contrast, rice cultivated in some fadama areas relied primarily on rainfall rather than direct river irrigation (Mohammed, personal communication, December 22, 2025).

The overdependence on weather and climatic elements for rice farming amongst smallholder rice farmers in Lokoja increases exposure to climate variability (IPCC, 2022). These farmers who use the floodplains of the confluence as farming ground experience these changes first, as they have limited capacity to absorb climate shocks. Flooding events in Lokoja submerge rice fields, destroy seedlings, delay planting, and also wash away stored produce. In most cases, irregular rainfall has been shown to disrupt planting calendars and reduce yields (Folorunsho and Ajiwoju, 2024). These impacts affect women differently because of existing social and economic inequalities.

Climate shocks among smallholders' women rice farmers.

Over the past decade, Lokoja has experienced severe and recurrent flooding, notably in 2012, 2020, and 2022, resulting in the destruction of thousands of hectares of rice fields. For women farmers, who often lack the financial capacity to recover from repeated climate shocks, climate change functions as a threat multiplier, deepening existing

gender inequalities and economic vulnerability. Studies indicate that women constitute a substantial proportion of smallholder rice farmers in Lokoja and play a critical role in the town's agro-economy (Ameh et al., 2021). They are actively involved in land preparation, planting, weeding, harvesting, processing, and marketing (FAO, 2011). These activities support household income and food security for many families.

Despite their significant contribution, women farmers control fewer productive resources. Access to land, credit, farm inputs, extension services, and climate information remains limited. In many areas around Lokoja, land is controlled by the kings and distributed by the chiefs. Customary land ownership in Irenedu–Koton Karfe is vested in the traditional authority. According to HRH Alhaji Mohammed Jubrin, the Zigu of Irenedu–Koton Karfe (personal communication, December 27, 2025), "Land belongs to the king (Ohimeje). The chiefs are instructed to allocate portions of land to every family, including women. After harvest, people pay tribute to the king. The amount depends on how fruitful the harvest is. Farmers are not forced to pay; they give willingly."

Women smallholder rice farmers remain critical to rice farming, processing, and marketing, yet they often lack secure land tenure, financial services, agricultural extension support, and timely climate information (FAO, 2011). These are some of the constraints that weaken women's capacity to respond effectively to climate stress, contributing to low yields and poor harvests. Due to limited adaptive capacity, shifting weather patterns lead to widespread uncertainty, particularly in rural and peri-urban communities. Many women rice farmers have observed environmental changes without fully understanding climate change, leaving them poorly prepared to manage its impacts. Women rice farmers in Lokoja reported limited but inconsistent access to post-flood support.

Aminat Adamu (personal communication, December 27, 2025) described a government-led credit intervention following the 2012 flooding: "After the 2012 flood, the government brought representatives to help women rice farmers open bank accounts. We were given access to ₦150,000 loans with very small interest. It helped us, but it was not really enough". Although some climate-related training was provided, participants emphasised the lack of sustained support.

According to Khadijat Musa (personal communication, December 22, 2025), she confirmed that some farmers received training "Yes, we received flood and climate change training, but there was no follow-up to check if those who were trained are doing well." One of the respondents, Zainab Jubrin from Shintaku (personal communication, December 28, 2025), confirmed that she was among the women rice farmers who received support in the form of training and farm inputs. She noted that assistance was provided by both federal and state governments, as well as development and humanitarian agencies such as ACRE SAL, HYPPADEC, and the Red Cross.

During the period under study, climate change-induced yield losses have contributed significantly to reduced rice output in Lokoja and its environs, climate shocks directly impacted households, and there was an increase in food insecurity and poverty in the area under study. Repeated flooding in Lokoja led to economic and job loss among many women rice farmers. Many rice fields were swept away, and farmers have to wait for

the water to subside before they can return to farming, resulting in delayed or failed planting. Some rice farmers who stored their grains in a warehouse along the Lokoja-Ankpa road and beach road had their grains swept away. Rising temperatures increased pest and disease pressure.

The economic strain caused by the loss of harvest, which is the primary source of income for many women farmers, affected household nutrition and the ability to pay for children's education. Women who more often than not shoulder the responsibility of managing household food provisions complained that they have to engage in other trading activities and menial jobs because rice farming is no longer sustainable. Among the participants, Hajara Sule, a former rice farmer in Lokoja, said she lost all her rice cultivation following the 2012 flooding. She had to quit farming because she could not obtain financial help from the government (Hajara Sule, personal communication, December 22, 2025).

Rukayat Adamu from Koton Karfe (personal communication, December 27, 2025) explained that flooding not only disrupts farming activities but also severely disrupts children's education. During flood periods, movement becomes restricted as schools and surrounding infrastructure are submerged. Many teachers leave affected communities and return to Lokoja town, only coming back after the floodwaters recede. As a result, regular schooling is suspended for extended periods. In some cases, communities attempt to continue learning by setting up temporary structures made from zana (woven grasses) used to construct makeshift huts or tents. However, these spaces are poorly suited for teaching and learning.

She further noted that children face serious safety risks during floods, particularly snake bites, which become more frequent as water levels rise. Access to timely medical care is often limited because flooding restricts movement to urban centres or well-equipped hospitals. When treatment is delayed, such incidents can lead to loss of life (Oludare and Aliu, 2013). Because of these challenges, education is often halted until the flood season ends, leading to prolonged interruptions and delays in children's schooling. Over time, some children become discouraged and eventually withdraw from education entirely. Rukayat said that although flooding has a health impact because there are higher cases of malaria, fever and typhoid due to stagnant waters that contribute to mosquito breeding, food scarcity is common. Flooding leads to an abundance of fish and other aquatic animals that increase protein intake temporarily (Rukayat Adamu, personal communication, December 27, 2025).

Climate-induced challenges among rice farmers lower farm yields and heighten cultivation risks, making recovery increasingly difficult for smallholder rice women farmers. Structural disadvantages further compound these challenges. Within a largely patriarchal social system, women face limited access to land ownership, restricted access to credit and insurance, low participation in extension programmes, and heavy unpaid care responsibilities. These factors constrain the adoption of adaptation measures such as improved seed varieties, irrigation, and mechanisation. Evidence suggests that women farmers adapt less to climate change, not due to lack of knowledge, but because of limited access to resources and societal structures (Doss, 2017).

Despite poor access to climate information, many of the smallholder women rice farmers have adopted various local coping mechanisms, including adjusting the farming calendar to avoid peak flood months, forming groups to pool resources and access small-scale loans. However, these coping strategies are not sustainable and weaken long-term resilience. These strategies are often insufficient against severe climate events. Institutional support remains weak. Gender-blind climate policies fail to address women's specific needs. Many women rice farmers in Lokoja have had to quit rice cultivation for other economic activities. Despite their resilience, women remain underserved by extension services. They lack access to modern "Climate-Smart Agriculture" (CSA) techniques, as well as access to flood-resistant rice varieties (e.g., FARO 44) due to high costs or lack of awareness (Ameh et al., 2021).

The study finds that the future of rice production in Lokoja is closely tied to the adaptive capacity of the most vulnerable farmers, particularly women. A sustainable and environmentally responsible response to climate change requires the Kogi State government and non-governmental organisations to move beyond broad, gender-neutral policies and adopt gender-responsive climate interventions. These should include direct access for women farmers to flood-tolerant rice varieties, affordable credit, and timely, location-specific climate information. Safeguarding the livelihoods of women rice farmers is therefore not only an environmental issue but also a matter of social justice and human rights within the Niger–Benue floodplain.

Historical evidence suggests rice farming has always had a key impact on the economics of the area, and women's contribution is central to the rice economy. However, smallholder women rice farmers remain largely excluded from formal agricultural support and policy benefits. The study finds that many existing climate adaptation frameworks are top-down and patriarchal, with limited engagement with the lived experiences and historical realities of smallholder women rice farmers. Hence, without a bottom-up and context-sensitive approach, such policies will fail to produce effective outcomes.

The findings further show that climate change is not gender-neutral. Both men and women are affected, but existing social structures intensify the impacts on women. In Lokoja and its environs, smallholder women rice farmers face distinct constraints related to land access, finance, training opportunities, and participation in decision-making. These barriers limit their ability to adopt effective climate adaptation strategies and increase their exposure to climate risks. The study further highlights that smallholder women rice farmers in Lokoja are at the frontlines of the climate crisis. Although many demonstrate adaptive strategies and local knowledge, their efforts are constrained by persistent gender gaps in access to productive resources. Climate change affects women more severely than men, and inversely it will have a greater impact on local economies because women are linked to central roles in food production, household care, health, and informal economies.

Climate change further reduces access to fertile land, water, food, and stable livelihoods through flooding, droughts, rising temperatures, and erratic rainfall. In climate-stressed areas such as Lokoja, women and girls often walk longer distances to fetch water, spend extended hours on farms, or are withdrawn from school due to declining household income. Patriarchal social structures in Lokoja and across Nigeria intensify these

pressures. When resources become scarce, women and girls are typically the first affected. Disrupted education, early marriage, and exposure to physical risks during water collection deepen women's vulnerability to climate impacts.

Finally, the study finds that women rice farmers in Lokoja receive significantly less attention than male farmers in climate-related research, policy formulation, and intervention programmes. This imbalance is reflected in data collection processes, where male farmers dominate survey samples. As a result, women, despite their substantial contributions to rice cultivation, processing, and marketing, remain marginalised in climate adaptation and resilience-building initiatives.

1.4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Climate change acts as a multiplier of existing gender inequality in Lokoja. While both men and women are affected, smallholder women rice farmers experience deeper and longer-lasting impacts due to limited access to land, credit, training, and decision-making platforms. Government interventions and agricultural programmes largely target male farmers, slowing technological transfer and adaptation among women. This neglect undermines rice productivity, household food security, and local economic stability.

The continual marginalisation of smallholder women rice farmers in Lokoja weakens the overall resilience which climate adaptation planning is supposed to achieve. Without addressing gender-based structural barriers, climate policies and agricultural interventions will remain ineffective and unequal. Climate change and gender inequality interact to shape the experiences of women rice farmers in Lokoja, Kogi State. Women face higher risks but receive less support (Ameh *et al.*, 2021). Addressing climate impacts on rice farming requires gender-responsive adaptation policies. These should improve women's access to land, finance, extension services, and climate information. Without targeted action, climate change will continue to deepen poverty and food insecurity among smallholder women farmers, and in extension, the state.

For smallholder women farmers, who contribute extensively to the cultivation and production of the bulk of the region's rice, the impact of climate change is not a distant threat but a daily reality. Their lack of knowledge about climate change, environmental degradation and shifting weather patterns disproportionately affects and will reverse any gains made in poverty alleviation and regional development.

Having identified the impacts of climate change on smallholder women rice farmers in Lokoja, this paper provides the following recommendations. Effective climate adaptation and agricultural policies must explicitly address the specific vulnerabilities faced by smallholder women rice farmers. Both federal and state governments should prioritise gender-responsive adaptation strategies that recognise women's limited access to productive resources and decision-making platforms. In particular, women farmers require secure land-use rights, access to affordable credit and insurance schemes, and timely access to essential farm inputs to strengthen their resilience to climate-related shocks.

Beyond policy design, institutional support systems must be strengthened to ensure that women are actively included in climate adaptation efforts. Climate adaptation

training, early-warning systems, and agricultural extension services should be tailored to smallholder women farmers' needs and delivered through channels that are accessible to them. Targeted support for improved rice processing technologies is also necessary, as enhanced processing capacity can improve rice quality, reduce post-harvest losses, and increase household income among smallholder women farmers.

In addition, government agencies and civil society organisations should expand climate change awareness and preparedness programmes within Lokoja communities. Improved understanding of climate risks will support informed decision-making and early response to climate hazards. Given the persistent and unpredictable flooding along the Niger–Benue floodplains, the Kogi State government should consider long-term risk reduction measures, including the relocation of highly exposed farming communities to safer areas and the provision of appropriate irrigation infrastructure to support sustainable rice cultivation.

1.5. References

- Abbas, A., & Mayo, Z. A. (2021). Impact of temperature and rainfall on rice production in Pakistan. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 23(2), 1706–1728.
- Abdulazeez, R. O., Abdulrahman, S., & Oladimeji, Y. U. (2019). Economic diversification strategies of farmers under the Kogi Accelerated Rice Production Programme (KARPP). *Nigerian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 9(1), 56–69.
- Agbamu, J. (2015). Performance evaluation of the Kogi State Agricultural Development Programme since the withdrawal of World Bank assistance. *Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 60, 77–87. <https://doi.org/10.2298/JAS1501077A>.
- Ahmed, A., Saliu, O. A., Simon, D., & Bolukale, O. A. (2024). Climate change adaptability among urban residents of Lokoja, Nigeria. *Fuwukari Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(2).
- Akinwale, A. J., & Udochukwu, I. S. (2025). The role of environmental policy in Nigeria's climate resilience. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Social Sciences and Strategic Management Techniques*, 11(1).
- Alabi, S. I., Saddiq, N. M., & Abudu, S. (2024). Factors influencing adoption of recommended rice production practices in selected local government areas of Kogi State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology*, 4(4B).
- Ali, A. (2011). Ethnic relations in Lokoja in the colonial period. *Journal of History and Diplomatic Studies*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.4314/jhds.v4i1.68463>.
- Ameh, O. E., et al. (2021). Gender dimension of poverty among rice farmers in Kogi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agricultural Economics, Management and Development*, 9(1).
- Danjibo, N. D., Adesoji, A. E., & Oladayo, O. S. (2019). The relationship between flooding and food security in Kogi State. *African Journal of Environment and Natural Science Research*, 2(2), 31–47.
- Das, L., et al. (2022). A case study on gender differentiated role analysis in rice farming in a rice-intensive ecology (pp. 707–714).
- Doss, C. R. (2017). Women and agricultural productivity: Reframing the issues. *Development Policy Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dpr.12243>.

- Enesi, P. (2019). History, economy and society of Lokoja. Nigerian Defence Academy.
- Federal Ministry of Environment(FME). (2021). National climate change policy for Nigeria (2021–2030).
- FloodList. (2020, September 22). Nigeria – Widespread flooding in Kogi State after Niger River overflows. FloodList.
- Folorunsho, J. O., & Ajiwoju, M. (2024). Analysis of perceived effects of rainfall variability on rice yield in Lokoja, Kogi State. In Proceedings of the 14th Nigeria Association of Hydrological Sciences Conference.
- International Rice Research Institute. (2021, March 8). Women in rice farming [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=flP2ogyRDMM>.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change(IPCC). (2022). Climate change 2022: Impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability (H.-O. Pörtner et al., Eds.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844>.
- Itodo, D. S. (2017, December 28). How Fadama is turning Kogi into a rice production hub. Daily Trust. <https://dailytrust.com/how-fadama-is-turning-kogi-into-rice-production-hub/>.
- Muhammad, S. S. (2012). The impact of the 2012 floods on agriculture and food security in Nigeria using GIS. Paper presented at the United Nations International Conference on Space-Based Technologies for Disaster Management, Beijing, China.
- Okosun, S. E., Patrick, R. A., & Banki, T. C. (2025). Assessment of flood menace in cities: Lokoja communities. *Journal of Geography and Earth Sciences*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.15640/jges.v13p1>.
- Olufemi, B., et al. (2023). Perceived effectiveness of JICA rice processing technologies among rice processors in Kogi State. *International Journal of Agricultural Management and Development*, 13(2), 115–126.
- Oludare, A. S., & Aliu, S. (2013). The impact of urban micro-climate change on human comfort in Lokoja, Nigeria. *Katsina Journal of Natural and Applied Sciences*, 3(2).
- Onoja, N., et al. (2024). Effect of Anchor Borrowers' Programme on rice yield in North-Central Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 28, 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jae.v28i3.8>.
- Shahbandeh, M. (2021). Total rice consumption worldwide from 2008/2009 to 2020/2021. Statista.
- Sunday, S. O., & Aribisala, J. O. (2020). Time series forecasting of rainfall in Lokoja, Kogi State. *International Journal of Latest Technology in Engineering, Management & Applied Science*, 9(3), 53.
- Yusuf, A. T., Yamma, M. A., & Jacho, D. S. (2025). Challenges of implementing rice anchor borrower programme for food security in Kogi State. *Kashere Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 3(4).